

BEHAVIOR OF CARBON FIBER ELECTROPLATED WITH BI-METALS

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Abstract

A technology of continuous electroplating of copper-nickel and copper-cobalt on carbon fiber has been studied. The coated fibers after vacuum heat treatment under different temperatures were examined by means of X-ray diffraction, energy spectrum analysis, metallographic microscopy and scanning electron microscopy.

The tensile test results of the coated fibers showed that the tensile strength of the bi-metal coated fibers treated above 1020 K decreased more rapidly than those coated with mono-metal.

The carbon fiber reinforced aluminum composite plates were made by means of vacuum hot pressed technology. The transverse section of the plates indicated that the wettability and penetrability between the coated fibers and aluminum were favourable.

Introduction

Metal matrix composite (MMC) materials have been under development for more than twenty years. They were first developed for applications in aerospace, because of their predominant properties, such as high specific strength, high specific rigidity, high toughness and impact properties, low sensitivity to temperature changes, high surface durability and low sensitivity to surface flaws etc. Boron reinforced aluminum MMC combines the outstanding strength, stiffness, and low density of the boron fiber with the fabricability and engineering reliability of an aluminum alloy (1). The main problem, however, remains in its high cost. Thus the alternate MMCs of aluminum reinforced with carbon / graphite fibers appear to offer the most advantages as MMCs and consequently have received the most attention in aerospace and industries. A review of the various carbon / graphite reinforced MMCs is given in reference (2). The main problems of such materials are poor wettability and interaction between carbon / graphite fiber and aluminum under high temperature, and thus there were various methods attempting to coat the carbon fiber with some metals to improve the wettability and prevent the mutual diffusion between carbon fiber and aluminum.

Based upon the solid solubility of carbon in copper nearly approaching zero and our experiments showing that the strength of carbon fiber coated with copper decreases less than those coated with nickel or cobalt, after exposure to high temperatures above 1020 K, we are conducting an experiment to see if there might be a barrier of copper to interrupt the diffusion interaction between nickel (or cobalt) and carbon, by means of carbon fiber coated with copper and cobalt, or coated with copper and nickel, in order to raise the tensile strength of the coated carbon fibers.

Experiments

Technology for electroplating

The average properties of carbon fiber, made in China, are listed in table I.

Table I. Properties of carbon fiber

diameter	density	tensile strength	modulus
μm	kg/m^3	MPa	GPa
6-8	1860-1870	1863-2225	133

The whole continuous electroplating installation (3), used to plate bi-metals on fiber surface, consists of a high temperature desizing furnace, activating treatment bath, plating tanks, automatic coiling and decoiling mechanism and electric accessories, as shown in figure 1 (a). Photoview of the installation has been shown in figure 1 (b).

The technological process may be divided into desizing, chemical

activation, electroplating and coiling.

(a)

(b)

Figure 1. (a) Sketch and (b) photo of the installation
1. uncoated fiber winding drum, 2. carbon fiber, 3. desizing
furnace, 4. rinsing, 5. activating treatment bath, 6. plating
tanks, 7. copper-pilot wheels 8. anode plate, 9. winding drum.

Desizing. The fibers were sized as received. Desizing process used is by heating the fiber to 970 K in nitrogen atmosphere, and then followed by a thorough rinsing.

Chemical activation. The authors select one or more types of chemical solvents to activate the fiber surface, thus allowing an even wetting of the carbon fiber surface and then a uniform covering of each single fiber. A water rinse following the activation will be necessary to prevent contamination of the electroplating tank.

Electroplating. Two types of continuous electroplating technological process are used: 1) coating of copper first, then nickel, and 2) coating of copper first, then cobalt. Continuous carbon fiber goes through the plating tank between the two long plan anodes, and the current applied by two conducting copper wheels on each side of the tank. The current density has to be controlled strictly, too high a voltage will fuse down and injure the fibers. The limiting voltage was 15-20 volts and the current was 0.5-1.2 amperes according to the plating solution selected. A thorough rinsing must follow the plating as well.

Coiling. The speed of feeding the fiber is controlled by automatic coiling and decoiling drums, which will also influence the thickness and quality of platings together with the production efficiency. Optimum plating speeds have to be selected according to the plating parameters, but generally a plating time of 40-120 s is enough for this installation.

After electroplating, the bi-metal coatings are continuous with the average thickness of about 0.7-1 μm . It is difficult to distinguish the bi-metal layers under light metallographic microscope, as shown in figures 2 and 3.

Figure 2. Metallograph of copper-nickel coating.

Using BD-78 type X-ray diffraction meter, the X-ray identification of phases has shown that there were copper, cobalt and nickel in the coatings.

Vacuum heat treatment

In order to study the interface interaction between carbon fiber and its coating elements under different temperatures, the coated fibers had been subjected to a vacuum heat treatment with vacuum of 5×10^{-5} torr. The treating temperatures selected were 470, 570, 670, 720, 770, 870, 920, 970, 1020, 1070, and 1120 K respectively. After heating to the desired temperature, soaking for one hour, the specimen was held within the furnace

Figure 3. Metallograph of copper-cobalt coating.

to cool to room temperature. Then the treated specimens were tested and analyzed with ZDM 250 Kilogram Tension Tester, BD-78 X-ray Diffraction instrument, and PSEM 500-X Energy Spectrum Meter, to determine the change of chemical composition, structure and properties, and to examine the micro-structure changes of the heat treated specimens under light metallographic Microscope and SEM.

Technology of the vacuum hot pressed composite plate

Packing the unidirectional bi-metal coated fiber laminates and LF-2 aluminum (similar to 5052 aluminum) foils alternately, and sandwiched with two LF21 aluminum (similar to 3003 aluminum) sheets, 0.5 mm in thickness, were installed in a stainless steel box. The box was then brazed, vacuumed and heated to the temperature range between solidus and liquidus of the selected aluminum alloys, i.e. 890-920 K, and pressed within the pressure range of 50-100 kg/cm², so as to see the possibilities of wetness between the coated fiber and the semi-liquid aluminum, and the availability of the technology of making a MMC plate. Figure 5 is the installation for hot vacuum compression. The plate obtained has shown that the technology of making such a plate is valid.

Results and analysis

Tensile strength

The tested results of tensile strength for the treated specimens are listed in table II and indicated in figures 5 and 6. The curves shown on the figures indicate that the strength of the bi-metal coated fibers decrease abruptly when treated above 1020 K.

Table II. The average tensile strength of the carbon fibers coated with copper-cobalt and copper-nickel

temperature K	tensile strength Cu-Co coated, MPa	tensile strength Cu-Ni coated, MPa
room	2107	2119
470	2047	2005
570	1931	1848
670	1911	1761
770	1809	1769
870	1859	1871
970	1878	1973
1020	1036	1907
1070	864	1090
1120	981	1041

Figure 4. Photograph of the installation for hot vacuum compression.

Metallographic observations

The coated layer of the fibers heat-treated below 1020 K indicates no obvious changes, observed under light metallographic microscope, as shown in figures 7 and 8. However, when treated above 1020 K, there appears serious abrasion, aggregation and broken, as shown in figures 9 and 10. But we did not find the phenomena described in reference (4, 5, 6). The appearances of the layer under scanning electron microscope are similar to those under light metallographic microscope, as shown in figures 11 and 12.

Energy spectrum analysis

The distribution of copper, nickel and cobalt along the radial direction of the coated carbon fiber, after different heat treatments, has been analyzed by using PSEM 500X Energy diffraction spectrometer, as shown in figure 1. The similar analysis for uncoated fiber also done, for comparison, is shown in figure 14. Due to the diffusion of carbon atoms under high temperature, a tendency of copper and cobalt atoms migrating to the

Figure 5. Variation of tensile strength of Cu-Co coated fibers with test temperature.

Figure 6. Variation of tensile strength of Cu-Ni coated fibers with test temperature.

Figure 7. Metallograph of the fiber coated with copper and nickel after heat treated at 970 K.

Figure 8. Metallograph of the fiber coated with copper and cobalt after heat treatment at 970 K.

Figure 9. Metallograph of the fiber coated with copper and nickel after heat treated at 1070 K.

Figure 10. Metallograph of the fiber coated with copper and cobalt after heat treated at 1070 K.

Figure 11. Scanning electron micrograph of the carbon fiber coated with copper and nickel after heat treated at 730 K.

Figure 12. Scanning electron micrograph of the carbon fiber coated with copper and nickel after heat treated at 830 K.

Figure.13. Elements distribution of the bi-metals coated layer along the radial direction of the fiber. 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 corresponds to 1070, 1020, 920, 570 K and room temperature respectively.

Figure 14. Elements distribution of the bi-metal coated and mono-metal coated fiber along the radial direction after treated at 1020 K. 1 and 2 indicate mono-metal and bi-metal coatings respectively. b-c means from boundary to center.

Figure 15. X-ray diffraction spectrum of the copper-nickel coated carbon fiber; (a) room temperature, untreated; (b) vacuum heat treated at 1070 K.

central portion of the carbon fiber would be occurred, as shown in these figures. It seems to be contradictory to the classical theory that the solubility of carbon in copper nearly approaches zero (7), the migration of copper atom in carbon is more than those of nickel or cobalt atom, when the treated temperature is higher than 1020 K. The mutual diffusion between copper atoms and carbon atoms promotes the breaking of the carbon bond, and the local graphitizing might be the cause of a decrease in fiber strength above 1020 K.

X-ray diffraction analysis

The analysis of X-ray diffraction for the bi-metal layers of carbon fiber, as shown in figure 15 and figure 16, has proven the following three facts: 1) The grain growth, sharpening of the spectrum and the obvious distinguished characteristic spectrum, appearing after high temperature treatment of 1070 K, will be the evidence that copper, nickel and cobalt existed in the bi-metal layers. 2) The average grain size of nickel and copper are increased, with the increased temperature, from 160 to 633 Å and from 130 to 370 Å in diameter respectively. 3) The two dimensional diffusion scattering of carbon fibers gradually changing into three dimensional diffusion scattering suggests that the structure of the carbon fiber has been graphitized locally under the catalysis of nickel and cobalt.

(a)

"PHOTO MISSING"

(b)

Figure 16. X-ray diffraction spectrum of the copper-cobalt coated carbon fiber: (a) room temperature, untreated; (b) vacuum heat treated at 1070 K.

Wettness of vacuum hot pressed MMC

The fibers are uniformly distributed within the aluminum matrix after vacuum hot pressing, and no extrusion of fibers appears at the fracture surface after tension test, as shown in 17 and 18. We may see that cracks are mainly coming from near the interface between the fiber and aluminum matrix, and appear as brittle fracture, as shown in figure 18.

Discussion of the tested results

Contradicting our assumption, the copper layer does not act as a barrier to interrupt the migration of nickel or cobalt inward to the central portion of the carbon fiber, and the copper itself migrates inward as well, so as to render good for evil that the strength of the bi-metal coated fibers is worse than mono-metal coated fibers, as shown in table III, in spite of the good wettability between the coated fibers and aluminum. The reason is not well known. It might be the alloying of copper and nickel (or cobalt) due to

Figure 17. Metallograph of copper-nickel coated fibers reinforced aluminum composite plate.

Figure 18. Fractograph of copper-nickel coated fibers Reinforced aluminum composite plate, SEM.

table III. Compare of the strength for bi-metal and mono-metal coated fibers

coated layer	tensile strength, MPa				
	1	2	3	4	5
Co	1180	1006	1212	1161	1503
Cu - Co	943	924	784	868	830
Ni	1040	1297	1226	1694	1188
Cu - Ni	1207	1075	1132	1056	981

diffusion at high temperature, so as to take the chance to bring nickel atoms in contact with carbon fiber surface, and introducing a mutual diffusion interaction among copper, nickel and carbon atoms. Once the atoms of nickel, copper and carbon migrate mutually, Jackson (8) and (9) considered that nickel and copper possess the catalytic effect on graphitizing. And thus, the strength for bi-metal coated carbon fibers decreases more severely than those coated with mono-metal.

Conclusions

1. The introduced technology and installation for continuous electroplating of copper-nickel and copper-cobalt on carbon fiber are successful to form coatings on carbon fiber.

2. The coated bi-metal fibers, under well chosen technological conditions, can be hot pressed with aluminum or aluminum alloy foils into MMC plate.

3. Since copper can not act as a barrier, the strength of copper-nickel or copper-cobalt coated carbon fibers is less than those coated with nickel or cobalt alone, when the coated fibers had been heat treated at temperature above 1020 K.

4. The metal coated carbon fiber reinforced aluminum composite materials, either after pressed or heat treated below 970 K, might be applicable for structural parts.

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